

IS SELF STUDY AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO IMPROVE WRITING SKILLS?

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Abstract: This article examines how students can study themselves individually and improve their writing skills. Also this article shows very effective techniques and tips for writing improvement.

Key words: Techniques, describing people, summary writing, reading every day, improving creative thinking.

Introduction. Writing is supposed to be one of the most difficult skills to improve among the other ones. The main reason for that is the fact that writing is a complete written form of one's thoughts, ideas, opinions and so on. Most people struggle with collecting all their thoughts to one place.

On the other hand, when it comes to examination – this struggle doubles and students' pressure will boost. So, can students themselves improve their writing skills without the teacher's help.

The level of students in English, their vocabulary treasure, their feelings during the exam all of them will impact on the writing examination result, but we have one thing which is never ever can be taken out or broken. This is the proficiency of writing on their own language. Not in English but in their mother tongue. There are lots of techniques and tips with the help of the L1.

Main part

Technique 1 – reading books every day and writing the summary. The more you read, the more words you gain exposure to, and they'll inevitably make their way into your everyday vocabulary.

Students can read the books in L1 or even in L2, it depends on them, after which they should write the summary of what they have read. The heroes of the book, the description of any detail they want, whether they agree or disagree with the author in some situations and so on.

In that situation, firstly students' memory is active and helps to gather necessary information in a written form.

Technique 2 – keeping journal. Why people keep journals? For some, the purpose of journaling can be as simple as trying to better understand their own

thoughts and feelings. Getting thoughts out of your head and onto paper can provide a new way to improve mental health.

Lots of people are interested in how this can help to improve that skill. If we write our daily plans and keep journal this is done every single day. That's why it is systematically becomes as a habit. Writing habit is formed and let's look at other techniques.

Technique 3 – writing about your day. Writing daily forces you to come up with new ideas regularly, and so that forces you to solve the very important problem of where to get ideas. What's the answer to that problem? Ideas are everywhere!

It is kind of storytelling but in a written form, story writing. Students should write about their day. Whom they met today, what the weather was like today, what kind of funny situations were and where did they go with their friends and etc.

Technique 4 – watching different lectures about writing on YouTube platform.

After students have developed their writing in their mother tongue and became more professional now they can watch necessary videos of different teachers on YouTube which is very useful. Because different teachers explain topics in a different way, so the distinction among different teachers is useful way to think in a more creative way.

Conclusion. All things considered, writing is not as difficult as it is supposed to be. It is just a skill which requires continuously developing and effort. Spelling words correctly is also necessary aspect of writing skill. Students undoubtedly should listen to the teachers' advice but it is not enough to be professional writer, that's why students should study extra at home and improve their writing skills. Since this is not a simple skill that can just be learned from a book. There is no rule or book that will teach you to become good at writing, it is a skill that requires a lot of effort.

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